

Reaction scheme/sample structure

ChemDraw File (linked):

Literature/reference experiments

Literature	
Reproduction	
Similar experiments	

Reagents

Name	CAS Number / Experiment Number	Inventory number	Amount [mmol]	Equivalents	Mass _{theo} [mg]	Mass _{exp} [mg]	Molar mass [g/mol]	Density (g/ml)	Volume [ml]	Concentration [mM]

Work-up and Analytical Reagents

Name	CAS Number / Experiment Number	Inventory number	Mass _{exp} [g]	Volume [ml]	Concentration [M]

Irradiation Parameters

Power measured using [Power Meter - 843-R-USB + 919P-020-12](#) unless specified otherwise.

For the determination of the power settings the Lamps app: <https://github.com/water-splitting-group/Lamps>.

	Name
Used Set-up	Equipment - Manual irradiation setup Equipment - Advanced irradiation setup V1.0 Equipment - Advanced power measurement setup V1.0

	Light Source Name	Used power source	Wavelength [nm]	Power Setting [mW]	Analogue Setting [-]
First light source					
Second light source					

Used beam combiner [Name or None]	
Irradiation distance [cm]	
Thermostat temperature [°C]	
Stirring speed [rpm]	
Start time [s], relative to start of log	
End time [s], relative to start of log	

Ultrasonication Parameters

Ultrasonication device	
Power output [W]	
Amplitude [%]	
Interval [s/s]	
Total ultrasonication time [min]	
Cooling method	

Microwave Parameters

SETTINGS	Run 1
Target Temperature [°C]	
Ramp	

Time	
Pre-stirring	
Vial Type	
Absorption Level	
Final Pressure [bar]	
Final Power [W]	
Photo of microwave parameters	

Column purification parameters

Information	Column 1	Column 2
Type of column/device used		
If applicable: PDF of autoflash		
Column width [cm]		
Column length [cm]		
Packing material		
Packing technique		
Eluent (including possible gradient)		

Furnace Parameters

Link the furnace/equipment that was used.

Temperature/time parameters

Used zone or charge sensor	
Used delayed start	
Used automatic/manual/extended holdback	
The temperature band entered for manual/extended holdback (°C)	
End time [min], relative to start of program	

Segments

	Target Temperature (°C)	Duration (h)	Rate (°C/h)	Temperature band (°C)	Description of the segment	Observations
First segment						
Second segment						
End segment						

Gas parameters

Used gas flow	
Gas pressure on the gas supplier [bar]	
Gas flow speed on the gas supplier [l/h]	
Used vacuum	
Start vacuum time [min], relative to start of program	
Start vacuum time [min], relative to start of program	

Procedure/observations

All steps (unless stated otherwise) were carried out under argon using either standard Protocol - Schlenk Technique or in an nitrogen filled glovebox (MBRAUN).

No metal was used during the synthesis or work-up besides metal cannulas.

The synthesis/reactions were performed in the dark by either wrapping the reaction flasks in aluminum foil or turning the lab light and light in the fume hood off, when the flasks were uncovered.

Date	Time	Step	Observations	Pictures

Analysis

Used calibration:

- GC:
- DPD-POD:
- pH-meter:

- FireSting:

Date	Time	Sample name	Analysis method	Analytical device	Solvent	Raw Data	Processed Data	Comparative Data	Interpretation

Comparative analytical data

Date	Time	Sample name	Analysis method	Analytical device	Solvent	Raw Data	Processed Data	Comparative Data	Interpretation

Product characterization

Sample	Mass [mg]	Purity	Mass _{pure} [mg]	Amount [μmol]	Yield [%]	Description	Image	Storage location

Results

Future recommendations

Old procedure	Problem	Suggested new procedure

Linked resources

Equipment - [Advanced irradiation setup V1.0 I](#)

Equipment - [Advanced power measurement setup V1.0 I](#)

Equipment - [Manual irradiation setup](#)

Power Meter - [843-R-USB + 919P-020-12](#)

Unique eLabID: 20250821-c9c893cf7dad30f78b0f88f850740096faefd23a
 Link: <https://elab.water-splitting.org/experiments.php?mode=view&id=2738>